

BOND PERFORMANCE OF PRESTRESSED CFRP TO CONCRETE UNDER SERVICE FATIGUE LOADING AT HIGH TEMPERATURE

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the bond performance of prestressed carbon fiber reinforced polymer to concrete under service fatigue loading at high temperatures. Fatigue tests were performed in reinforced concrete beams at 4Hz, with minimum and maximum stress corresponding to 50% and 60% of the steel yielding obtained from the static 6-point bending test, and an R ratio of 0.60). The test conditions (5M cycles at ambient temperature, 5M cycles at 50°C, and 2M cycles at 75°C) reflect the typical degradation processes of conventional reinforced concrete bridges, in which the synergy between the high temperatures reached by the asphalt pavement and the service fatigue loading may shorten the frequency of maintenance operations. In the 5 to 10M cycles interval, the decrease of the adhesive's mechanical properties induced a shear stress redistribution with a decrease in the interfacial shear stresses due to the softer behavior of the adhesive. The high temperature raised the stiffness loss and induced local debonding in the 10 to 12M cycles interval, with no damage in the non-mechanical anchorage zone and the adjacent strengthening lengths. The combined effects of fatigue and temperature showed to be strongly influenced by the glass transition temperature of the epoxy resin and cyclic loading conditions and may induce interfacial debonding.

KEYWORDS

Temperature; fatigue; bonding; interfacial shear stress

INTRODUCTION

The bond performance of the FRP-to-concrete interface governs the failure modes and limits the effectiveness of FRP externally bonded reinforcement (FRP EBR) systems by restraining the use of the ultimate FRP tensile strength. (Garcez et al., 2008). Concrete cover delamination and interfacial debonding due to end or intermediate crack propagation are the main debonding failure modes related to FRP EBR systems (Triantafillou and Matthys, 2013). The FRP-to-concrete bond-slip relationship has been broadly modeled in the last decades (Brosens and Van Gemert, 1999; Dai et al., 2005; Ko et al., 2014; Monti et al., 2003; Nakaba et al., 2001; Savoia et al., 2007) based on the FRP bond length and axial stiffness, FRP/concrete width ratio, adhesive strength and stiffness, and concrete compressive strength. These models, validated through direct tensile and single or double shear tests, simulate the interface stress state for fracture modes I (normal stress) and II (axial stress). Debonding strength models developed in terms of tensile strength, simulating the fracture mode III, with normal and shear stresses induced at the FRP/concrete interface, have also been proposed (Chen and Teng, 2001; Teng et al., 2003). The current design codes suggest equations developed from models calibrated with experimental results to limit FRP stress levels and avoid interfacial debonding and concrete cover delamination (ACI Committee 440, 2017; Triantafillou and Matthys, 2013).

The effect of elevated temperatures on the FRP-to-concrete bond performance has attracted the attention of researchers in the last decades (Fernandes et al., 2020), mainly due to concerns regarding fire performance (Firmo et al., 2015). The bond properties of FRP systems have been proven to be closely related to the temperature gradient between the adhesive service temperature and the glass transition temperature (T_g) (Dong and Hu, 2016). Carlos et al. (Carlos and Rodrigues, 2018) have shown that the bond strength reduces continuously with the increase in temperature, reaching about 40% for temperatures near the T_g and 100% for temperatures higher than the T_g (Carlos and Rodrigues, 2018).

Some studies infer that high temperature induces debonding failure at the adhesive/FRP interface rather than at the concrete/adhesive interface (Di Tommaso et al., 2001; Tadeu and Branco, 2000). Most of these conclusions were obtained through the results of single and double-shear tests (Carlos and Rodrigues, 2018; Di Tommaso et al., 2001; Dong and Hu, 2016; Firmo et al., 2015; He et al., 2020; Petkova et al., 2014; Tadeu and Branco, 2000; Tajmir-Riahi et al., 2019), simulating fracture modes I (normal stress) and II (axial stress). Nevertheless, the stress state in a strengthened reinforced concrete (RC) beam corresponds to fracture mode III, with normal and shear stresses induced at the FRP/concrete interface (Teng et al., 2003). Thus, beam-type tests simulate the FRP debonding failure more accurately, especially when related to intermediate crack propagation, usually observed in bending experiments (Garcez et al., 2008). Klamer et al. (Klamer et al., 2008) experiments show that high temperatures may influence the flexural capacity of FRP-strengthened structural elements mainly due to the different materials' thermal expansion coefficients, the reduction of adhesive's elastic modulus, and the changes in failure mode. Although publications on the effect of heating on the flexural capacity of structural elements can be found in the literature (Ahmed and Kodur, 2011; Chowdhury et al., 2008), the effect of temperature on the bond performance and failure modes is relatively limited (Petkova et al., 2014), especially in full-scale specimens. The influence of high temperature on the wet layup FRP systems has already been evidenced by the decrease of the composite's ultimate strength and Young's modulus (Jarrah et al., 2018; Nguyen et al., 2018) due to changes in the epoxy mechanical properties (Firmo et al., 2019). Experiments by Machado et al. (Machado et al., 2019) show that increasing test temperature up to 80°C resulted in an increase of up to 50% in the FRP fracture energy in mode I, which can be explained by changes in the impregnating resin mechanical properties. Pultruded CFRP strips exposed to 98°C to 300°C and loaded under high temperatures up to failure, tested by Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2011), lost 30 to 50% of the ultimate strength and failed due to fiber rupture after softening and gasification of the epoxy matrix. Functional relationships to compute the strength as a function of temperature have been proposed and calibrated for different FRP systems (Gibson et al., 2005; Wang et al., 2011). Additionally, the temperature-dependent damage model formulated by Mivehchi & Varvani-Farahani (Mivehchi and Varvani-Farahani, 2010) has evidenced the high-temperature effects in FRP submitted to cyclic loading by decreasing fatigue strength and increasing cumulative fatigue damage.

The fatigue behavior of RC beams strengthened with FRP EBR systems has been broadly studied (Charalambidi et al., 2016; Dong et al., 2012; Zhang, 2016; Zhao et al., 2019), and different stress-cycle curves (S-N curves) have been proposed (Garcez et al., 2019; Meneghetti et al., 2017, 2014). However, Daud et al. (Daud et al., 2015) suggest the need for further investigations on the ultimate debonding strain reduction due to fatigue and post-fatigue loading regimes in full-scale structural elements to understand the extent of size effects and associated in situ stress states. Pullout double-face shear tests by Yun et al. (Yun et al., 2008) in EBR FRP systems under fatigue loading showed that the slip increase is much faster at the first fatigue cycles due to the higher energy dissipation related to initial microcracking. Sustained loading, by itself, decreases the FRP-to-concrete interfacial strength due to shear stress relaxation, compromising the FRP-to-concrete bonding performance (Gamage et al., 2016; Jeong et al., 2016).

The previously mentioned studies evaluate individual degradation processes or the combination of bond and temperature and bond and fatigue. However, in real structures, especially bridges, the bond performance of FRP EBR systems can be affected by the combined effects of temperature and fatigue. Huang et al. (Huang et al., 2011) proved that temperature changes in service conditions (i.e., 20°C to 80°C) could decrease the fatigue limits of FRP-strengthened RC elements. One of the few reports on the effects of fatigue and temperature in prestressed EBR FRP systems published by Gallego et al. (Gallego et al., 2018) showed no evidence of steel reinforcement fatigue failure after 2 million load cycles (steel stress range $\Delta\sigma_s = 129\text{MPa}$ and the ratio of the minimum and maximum loads $R = 0.75$) being applied in large-scale slabs under 50°C and tested as cantilever elements. However, Gallego et al. (Gallego et al., 2016) suggest that more large-scale tests are necessary to evaluate the behavior of prestressed EBR FRP and the gradual anchorage system in real concrete structures, figuring out elevated temperature scenarios.

In this context, this paper discusses the combined effects of service fatigue loading and high temperature applied in a full-scale RC beam strengthened with EBR prestressed FRP, focusing on the FRP-to-concrete bonding performance and the stability of the non-mechanical anchorage system. The results are assessed through the displacement at midspan vs. number of cycles vs. temperature, cracking, and interfacial shear stress. The assumptions adopted in the experimental program reflect the common degradation process of conventional RC bridges, especially those post-strengthened with EBR prestressed FRP, in which the synergy between the high temperatures reached by the asphalt pavement and the service fatigue loading may shorten the frequency of maintenance operations.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The experimental procedure involves testing of two simply supported RC beams strengthened with two prestressed CFRP strips of span 6.5m, namely one tested under static loading as the control beam (PFRP_S), and the other beam (PFRP_F_T) tested under cyclic loading, details provided in Figure 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1: Strengthened RC beams.

Table 1: Experimental procedure design.

Specimen	Cross Section		Strengthening		Cyclic Loading		
	A_c (mm ²)*	A_s (mm ²)	A_f (mm ²)	Prestressing level on the strips	Min-Max stress**	Min – Max loads (kN)***	Frequency (Hz)****
PFRP_S	220.000	792	120	35% of ϵ_{fu}	-	-	-
PFRP_F_HT	220.000	792	120	35% of ϵ_{fu}	50% - 60%	68 - 78	4

* Concrete compressive strength 44MPa at 28 days; ** Related to the yielding of steel rebars in the beam tested under static loading; *** Including RC beam self-weight; **** frequency chosen to simulate conventional civil engineering structures (Demers, 1998).

The strengthening scheme consists of two Carbodur S 512 strips (1.2mm thick, 50mm wide, tensile strength 2,800MPa, ultimate strain 17‰, and Young's Modulus 165GPa) attached to the beam with the Sikadur®30LP thixotropic epoxy adhesive (Young's Modulus 10GPa, T_g 45°C if cured for seven days at 23°C and 72°C if cured for two h at 80°C). The prestressing operation was executed with the prestressing device (Meier et al., 2002), able to apply the non-mechanical anchorage known as the gradual anchorage system detailed in Figure 1, based on the gradual prestressing force release combined with the epoxy resin accelerated curing.

The test was designed to simulate degradation due to high temperature at service fatigue loading with the beam submitted to a stress range of 50% to 60% of the yielding stress (Table 1). The ACI 215R

(ACI Committee 215, 1997) code limits the stress range and upper stress in the reinforcing steel to 138 MPa and 80% of the yielding stress, whereas the updated ACI PCR- 215-21 mentions a maximum constant amplitude fatigue stress range of 124MPa based on the AASHTO LRFD bridge design specifications (AASHTO, 2017). The ACI 440.2R (ACI Committee 440, 2017) code limits the maximum stress in CFRP strengthening to 55% of the ultimate tensile strength. Meneghetti et al. (Meneghetti et al., 2011) reported that the steel reinforcement behavior dominates the fatigue failure of FRP-strengthened beams, and the respective S-N curves exhibit a shallower slope than those for un-strengthened beams. The fatigue life model developed by Garcez et al. (Garcez et al., 2019), specifically for RC beams strengthened with prestressed FRP, predicts the steel stress range corresponding to the 5% fractile curve at 2M cycles as 147.05 MPa. The beam tested under cyclic loading was submitted to the first 5M cycles at room temperature, 5M cycles at 50°C, and 2M cycles at 75°C. After 12M cycles, the beam was kept in a temperature-controlled wooden box under 78kN (maximum fatigue loading), and the temperature was gradually increased up to failure. The range 50°C to 75°C represents the typical temperature reached by RC elements under asphalt pavements during summer periods in some countries, and the T_g of the epoxy adhesive, respectively.

During the cyclic loading test, the applied loads, deflections, and the specific strains of concrete, steel, and FRP were monitored and recorded (Figure 2). The displacements at midspan were obtained through two Linear Variable Differential Transformers (LVDT) placed at the top of the beam. Specific strains of concrete were measured by a strain gauge placed on the bottom face of the beam at midspan. Strain gauges were also installed on the steel reinforcement and CFRP strips at the midspan. Manual records of displacement gauges (DG) provided information on the specific strain and shear stress distribution along the CFRP strips. Crack propagation was monitored, and crack opening records were captured through visual inspection.

Figure 2: Instrumentation.

The shear stress at the CFRP-to-concrete interface over the entire strip length was determined through Eq. 1, based on the static equilibrium and the linear behavior of the CFRP. In Eq. 1, τ_i is the average interfacial bond stress in section i , E_f and t_f are the elastic modulus and thickness of the CFRP $\varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_{i-1}$ is the strain variation on the CFRP strip between two measurements at the interval length Δ_x .

$$\tau_i = \frac{E_f t_f (\varepsilon_i - \varepsilon_{i-1})}{\Delta_x} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 3 shows the load versus displacement at midspan for the control beam PFRP_S and beam PFRP_F_HT at different stages. The black solid curve of Figure 3 represents the beam tested monolithically until failure. The colored lines show the displacements of beam PFRP_F_HT obtained with the beam unloaded and at the maximum fatigue loading after a certain number of cycles. The upper (78kN) and lower (68kN) fatigue loads correspond to 50%/60% of the yielding of steel rebars (128kN) and 48%/42% of the ultimate load of beam PFRP_S (162kN). As the fatigue loading is slightly higher than the cracking load (58kN), the displacements obtained since preloading are higher than those of PFRP_S. PFRP_F_HT shows a gradual loss of stiffness after 5M cycles applied at ambient temperature. The change in the slope of the curves after the subsequent 5M cycles applied at 50°C represents the stiffness loss due to the combined effects of temperature and fatigue. The last 2M cycles applied at

75°C, resulted in the most significant loss of stiffness, which is related to the decrease of the adhesive elastic modulus once it reached the T_g of the Sikadur®30LP (72°C if cured for two h at 80°C).

Figure 3: Load versus displacements at midspan.

The increasing midspan displacements due to the combined effects of cyclic loading and temperature, illustrated in Figure 4, show three stages of stiffness degradation: a rapid increase during initial cycles, followed by a stabilized increase in the intervening cycles up to 10M cycles, and a rapid increase from 10M to 12M cycles. The midspan displacements measured at the upper fatigue load increased by 30% from preloading to 1M cycles and only 4% up to 5M cycles. In the following 5M cycles, applied at 50°C, the midspan displacements increased by 14%. From 10M to 12M cycles, applied under 75°C (adhesive T_g), the midspan displacement increased by 42%. After 12M cycles, both strips presented local CFRP-to-concrete debonding in the loading region between cracks g and v (strip 01) or d and v (strip 02) of Figure 5. In both cases, the adjacent lengths of the strips remained connected to the concrete slab, and no signs of damage were identified in the gradual anchorage zone.

Figure 4: Increasing midspan displacements for beam PFRP_F_HT.

After 12M cycles, the temperature was gradually increased with the beam loaded at 78kN until failure. The failure occurred due to CFRP-to-concrete interfacial debonding after 30h, and the temperature reached 116°C. The CFRP-to-concrete interfacial debonding in both strips started from the border of

intermediate flexural cracks, where local debonding has been previously identified and propagated towards the adjacent support. Carlos et al. (Carlos and Rodrigues, 2018) proved through single-lap shear tests that the adhesive glass transition temperature does not necessarily represent the ultimate temperature of the CFRP-concrete interface. Beam PFRP_F_HT shows that, for the applied test condition, the accumulated fatigue and high-temperature damage after 10M cycles under the adhesive T_g resulted in a significant increase of midspan displacements, crack openings, and local CFRP-to-concrete debonding.

Figure 5: Crack pattern at the upper load for Beam PFRP_F_HT.

The CFRP interfacial debonding initiated between cracks named d and v, the region where the higher crack openings were observed. The crack patterns and openings at the upper fatigue load, presented in Figures 5 and 6, show the increasing number of cracks from the preloading up to 1M cycles, which resulted in a great loss of stiffness (2.78kN/mm to 2.13kN/mm). The number of cracks remained constant after 1M cycles, but the crack openings increased until failure, accompanied by a lower loss of stiffness. After 1M cycles, the stiffness reduced by 0.08kN/mm until 5M cycles at ambient temperature, 0.26kN/mm from 5M cycles to 10M cycles under 50°C, and 0.52kN/mm from 10M cycles to 12M cycles under 75°C. After 5M cycles, the maximum crack width was 0.22mm at the upper fatigue load. After 7.5M cycles, some cracks (g and i) changed for Y shape, but the maximum crack width at the upper fatigue load remained 0.22mm. After 10M cycles, the maximum crack width at the upper fatigue load reached 0.30mm. No manual crack opening measurements were made after 10M cycles for safety reasons. The gradual anchorage zone remained uncracked without any sign of debonding up to the failure of beam PFRP_F_HT. Following the CFRP-to-concrete interfacial debonding, the external loads were transferred to the steel rebars, and the beam finally failed. After failure, part of the concrete cover was removed from the bottom of the slab, and broken steel rebars were identified (Figure 7(b)) along the crack i that crossed the slab from side to side (Figure 7(a)). Before the failure, the opening of this crack reached about 4mm under 78kN.

Figure 6: Crack openings for beam PFRP_F_HT.

Figure 7: Beam PFRP_F_HT: (a) crack i after failure; (b) broken rebars.

Figure 8 shows the interfacial shear stress along the beam PFRP_F_HT, determined through Equation 1, using the strains presented in Figure 9. The results from both strips are reasonably symmetric about the midspan. The shear transfer mechanism is not influenced by the first 1M cycles applied at ambient temperature (green and light blue curves). From 5M (dark blue curves) to 7.5M (yellow curves) cycles, the interfacial shear stresses do not change significantly at the anchorage zone, but a decrease can be observed at the peaks in the center of the free span, which is compatible with the increase of local joint degradation (Zheng et al., 2013). There is also a shear stress redistribution to areas subjected to lower shear stress levels that become more critical when a certain epoxy temperature threshold is reached (Gallego et al., 2016) due to the decrease of the adhesive elastic modulus at elevated temperatures. A decrease in the interfacial shear stresses can be observed when 10M cycles are reached (orange curves) due to the softer adhesive behavior caused by the temperature increase. At 12M cycles, the interface degradation is clearly identified by the red interfacial shear stress curves, which ratify the local CFRP-to-concrete debonding identified at failure. The first peak stress in the curves of Figure 8 corresponds to the release of the prestressing force. The peak stresses close to the cracks named o, f, u and p, h, i can be related to the sudden shear stresses originated by flexural crack openings that induced the debonding failure by intermediate crack propagation (Kurtz et al., 2008).

The failure mode of slab PFRP_S tested monolithically was interfacial debonding due to end crack propagation. On the other hand, the debonding failure of slab PFRP_F_HT started from the border of intermediate flexural cracks, where local debonding has been previously identified and propagated towards the support. The combined effects of temperature and fatigue influenced the failure mechanism of slab PFRP_F_HT. The fatigue mechanism is complex and depends on several parameters, such as, for instance, cyclic creep of concrete and the flexural stiffness degradation due to the cracking increase and the modulus of rupture reduction under fatigue loading (Papakonstantinou et al., 2002). In the case of slab PFRP_F_HT, the accumulated fatigue damage in the steel rebars, added to the changes in the adhesive and concrete mechanical properties due to high temperature induced the local FRP-to-concrete debonding that resulted in the slab failure under the conditions mentioned above after 12M cycles. No damages occur in the concrete up to 120°C, but cracking, cementitious paste dehydration with volume reduction, and elasticity model reduction may occur for temperatures in the range of 120-250°C (Rohden et al., 2020). Loss of mechanical properties in the epoxy adhesive can be noticed once the glass transition temperature is reached (Firmo et al., 2019).

The maximum strain measured at upper fatigue load at 12M (5M at ambient temperature, 5M at 50°C, 2M at 75°C) cycles was about 10.6‰. The maximum strain increased only from 8‰ at 5M cycles (ambient temperature) to 8.30‰ after more 5M cycles at 50°C. From 10M to 12M at 75°C, the strain increased by about 2.3‰ due to combined effects of fatigue and temperature: broken steel reinforcement, concrete cracking, and mechanical properties loss of the adhesive at 75°C (approximately the glass transition temperature). The maximum stress after 10M cycles reached about

48% of the ultimate CFRP strain (17‰), complying with the recommendations of ACI 440.2R (ACI Committee 440, 2017), CSA S6-14 (Canadian Standard Association., 2014), and JSCE (Japanese Society of Civil Engineers, 1997) for sustained plus cyclic loading: 55%, 65%, and 70%, respectively. After more 2M cycles at 75°C, the maximum strain reached about 62% of the ultimate CFRP strain. The ACI 440.2R (ACI Committee 440, 2017) code recommends that the anticipated service temperature be 15°C below the glass transition temperature of the epoxy adhesive. The results presented in this paper corroborate the afore recommendation since significant strain increments were observed only after 10M cycles when the cyclic loading was applied at 75°C. The same code advises that the strength of externally bonded FRP systems must be assumed as wholly lost in a fire event unless an FRP fire-protection system exists. In a fire event, all applicable service loads must be resisted by the structural member without the FRP system, and strengthening limits can be used to avoid collapse.

Figure 8: Interfacial shear stress for beam PFRP_F_HT: (a) Strip 01; (b) Strip 02.

Experiments performed by Huang et al. (Huang et al., 2011) under a stress level (P_{max}/P_u) range of 0.60 to 0.84 showed a decrease in the fatigue limit of RC beams strengthened with CFRP EBR systems as the test temperature increased from 5°C to 80°C. In the prediction model of Huang et al. (Huang et al., 2011), the fatigue limit decreased sharply from 5°C to 40°C but much less from 40°C to 80°C. However, it is essential to highlight that the model cannot be indistinctly used to predict FRP-strengthened elements' fatigue vs. temperature behavior. First, the effect of temperature is strongly related to the T_g of the epoxy resin. Additionally, the fatigue behavior depends on the loading frequency and combined effects of the mean stress, steel stress range, and stress ratio. These parameters vary considerably in experiments and real applications. For example, the present paper's experiment does not fit the model above. For a stress level (P_{max}/P_u) of 0.48 (service fatigue loading), beam PFRP_F_HT performed adequately up to 10M even being the last 5M run under 50°C (T_g of Sikadur®30LP equal to 72°C if cured for two h at 80°C). The beam reached 12M cycles at 75°C, and the failure occurred just after the

gradual temperature increased up to 116°C under the upper fatigue loading. An equivalent CFRP-strengthened RC beam tested under a stress level of 0.67 at ambient temperature (Garcez et al., 2019) failed after only 331k cycles, which ratifies the stress level effect on the fatigue life. Another point to be considered is that FRP prestressing has also been shown to positively influence the fatigue performance of strengthened RC beams (Garcez et al., 2019).

Figure 9: FRP strain for beam PFRP_F_HT: (a) Strip 01; (b) Strip 02.

The lack of predictive models to consider the combined effects of temperature and fatigue in the flexural capacity of FRP-strengthened RC beams is still a research gap. Running experiments of full-scale beams with varying test temperatures, steel stress range, mean stress, and stress ratio demands extensive and expensive experimental campaigns, usually not viable from the perspective of time and economics. Thus, the combined effects of fatigue and temperature on the bonding performance of prestressed CFRP of a full-scale RC beam, discussed in the present manuscript, are valuable to ratify the strengthening system performance and the stability of the non-mechanical anchorage system under the considered test conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper discussed how the combined effects of service fatigue loading and high temperature influence the FRP-to-concrete bonding performance and the stability of the non-mechanical anchorage system in a full-scale RC beam strengthened with an EBR prestressed system. The following conclusions can be drawn:

The 10M cycles applied under service fatigue loading below the T_g induced shear stress redistribution due to cracking but did not lead to failure.

The 2M cyclic applied above the T_g raised the stiffness loss and induced local debonding even in service conditions but did not lead to failure or damage to the non-mechanical anchorage system.

The failure occurred just when the temperature was gradually increased above the glass transition temperature with the beam under the sustained upper fatigue loading.

The synergic effects of fatigue and temperature showed to be strongly influenced by the glass transition temperature of the epoxy resin and cyclic loading conditions.

The full-scale experiment simulating the typical degradation process of conventional RC bridges ratifies the FRP strengthening system performance and the stability of the non-mechanical anchorage system under the considered test conditions.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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